

Mainstreaming Climate Adaptation into Sectoral Policies in Seychelles

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Introduction

Small Island Developing States (SIDS) are generally considered highly vulnerable to climate change because they suffer from inherent environmental challenges linked to their smallness, remoteness, and exposure to natural hazards (Scandurra et al., 2018). While uncertainties exist regarding the timing, magnitude, and distribution of climate-related impacts on ecosystems, local livelihoods, and societies, there is high confidence that the global climate is changing and that this will significantly impact societies and the environment (IPCC, 2021). Moreover, climate variability and change, without effective adaptation and mitigation measures, will constrain nation-states from achieving their Sustainable Development Goals. This is especially the case for SIDS (Robinson, 2017) and other developing countries, due to limits to their adaptive capacity, also known as their adaptation deficit (Fankhauser and McDermott, 2014). Some of these limits are connected to available resources (financial, human, and technological), political and organizational factors. The mainstreaming of climate change adaptation into national development programmes and policies is at the core of Seychelles' Nationally Determined Contributions to addressing climate change. This has also gained traction in the nexus approach for Water-Energy-Food to increase the adaptive capacity of developing countries, most of which depend on climate-sensitive economic activities (Pardoe et al., 2017).

Even with much-publicized mitigation strategies, such as net zero emissions (Freak, 2021), improving the adaptive capacity of developing countries and SIDS is critical if sustainable development is to be achieved. Even if net zero emissions are achieved, the lifespan and impacts of greenhouse gases extend beyond the emission phase and adaptation will still be required. For example, life-cycle analysis based on carbon isotopes has proven that fossil-fuel carbon dioxide requires nearly 100 years to disintegrate into the atmosphere (Archer et al., 2009). Consequently, adaptation to climate change is considered necessary by development agencies and is promoted by the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the 2015 Paris Agreement's Nationally Determined Contributions. For SIDS in particular, adaptation to global climate change is a priority and has been described as a critical requirement among these countries (Nurse and Moore, 2005). In another study by Robinson (2017), the importance of adaptation to climate change as a pathway for SIDS to achieve

sustainable development is clearly emphasized. To ensure adaptation occurs, two options are available to policymakers and development practitioners: i) to integrate adaptation objectives into existing sectoral policies, strategies, and action plans or ii) to develop stand-alone adaptation policies and programmes (Runhaar et al., 2016).

Nationally, institutions play a crucial role in mainstreaming climate adaptation into sectoral policies as they provide an enabling environment (ensuring policies translate to actions and effective collaboration), as well as access to necessary resources (financial, human, and technological) that help to ensure implementation (Cuevas, 2018; Nkiaka and Lovett, 2018). Therefore, institutional support for adaptation is vital in overcoming the challenge of translating adaptation-related policies into actions for implementation and reducing the ‘implementation gap’, which is especially conspicuous in developing countries (Runhaar et al., 2018). Given that ‘the road to adaptation is always under construction’ (Etongo, 2021), knowledge of what makes mainstreaming effective is scarce and fragmented. The case of Seychelles represents a broader policy challenge relevant to a similar set of countries (e.g., vulnerable island states).

In addition to institutional participation and support, climate change is an increasingly multi-faceted problem that requires cross-departmental collaboration for solutions to be effective. But breaking through government silos is not always easy given that traditional policy-design processes often adopt a sector-based rather than a cross-sector approach. Mainstreaming is one approach to bring about adaptation and, in particular, contrasts with siloed sector-based approaches. While studies on mainstreaming climate adaptation into sectoral policies have been conducted in the Caribbean and Pacific SIDS (Robinson, 2017), Eastern, Central, and Southern Africa (Pardoe et al., 2017; Nkiaka and Lovett, 2018; England et al., 2018), little is known about the Indian Ocean SIDS, especially Seychelles. Adaptation is location and context specific, and such a study is crucial for Seychelles since adaptation is a national priority (Etongo, 2019). Therefore, this paper reviews the extent to which climate adaptation has been mainstreamed into sectoral policies in Seychelles, complemented by expert interviews to tease out barriers and how they might be overcome.

2. Conceptual perspective of adaptation mainstreaming

Integration or the articulation of information into policies and measures to improve the adaptive capacity of sectors and/or ecosystems to the impacts of climate change is known as mainstreaming (Ayers et al., 2014). Considering that it is easier to start with existing policies and practices rather than creating new or specific adaptation

policies, climate risks can more easily be incorporated into policies and practices that support short and long-term development planning. However, the effectiveness of climate adaptation mainstreaming requires insight into the drivers of mainstreaming and its barriers. Previous studies in Seychelles (Etongo, 2019), other SIDS (Robinson, 2017), and empirical research globally (Runhaar et al., 2018) have identified the following drivers and barriers to adaptation mainstreaming, which include: (i) political factors, (ii) timing, (iii) characteristics of the adaptation problem, (iv) cognitive factors, (v) resources, and (vi) organizational factors. These factors are a double-edged sword as they can either drive or hamper the adaptation mainstreaming process.

Mainstreaming is not a new concept. Its usage can be traced to other global development issues, such as gender inequality, poverty alleviation, millennium development goals, and ongoing sustainable development goals (Mogelgaard et al., 2018). Through its much-publicized Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC), the Paris Agreement has also maintained the momentum on addressing climate change and is driving several initiatives locally. Adaptation projects often provide opportunities for add-ons and co-benefits that are relevant for mitigation, as demonstrated by the ecosystem-based adaptation to climate change project in Seychelles (Etongo, 2021). The updated NDC of Seychelles (GoS, 2021) applies a sector approach with clearly defined timelines and adaptation actions to be implemented. However, the actualization of these targets largely depends on external donor funding, which can make it difficult to predict when particular projects will be implemented. Government support from the Environment Trust Fund (ETF) and the Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT), is insufficient to satisfy the domestic demand to address the adaptation needs of the country (Etongo, 2019). The lack of domestic funding results in the key challenges identified by Etongo (op.cit.) that act as barriers to climate change adaptation in Seychelles. Key challenges include human resources capacity, ineffective coordination and cooperation between government departments and the private sector, and lack of financial and technological resources.

Explicit definitions and unified frameworks are required for well-informed policy recommendations (Runhaar et al., 2018). The case of SIDS becomes even more relevant in this regard as Chapter 29 (Small Islands) of the Fifth Assessment Report of the IPCC indicates that more needs to be understood on practical approaches to achieve climate change adaptation mainstreaming in the context of SIDS (IPCC, 2022). Improving our understanding could begin with the mainstreaming strategies identified by Wamsler and Pauleit (2016), which can be used to better inform decision makers of adaptation mainstreaming at the policy, sector, programme, and project levels. Therefore, the current study assesses climate adaptation mainstreaming across six sectors as outlined in Seychelles' updated NDC (GoS,

2021) as follows: (i) forestry, (ii) energy, (iii) agriculture, (iv) water, (v) health, and (vi) blue economy (specifically coastal management, tourism, and fisheries).

3. Methods

A mixed method approach was adopted in the current study, including (i) an in-depth qualitative analysis of 25 policy documents (Table 1) and (ii) semi-structured interviews with 34 key stakeholders in relevant government ministries, institutions and other organizations (Table 2). A qualitative design offers a critical value which, according to Gephart (2004), provides a ‘description and understanding of the actual human interactions, meanings, and processes that constitute real-life organizational settings’. The method section is organized as follows: a review of relevant documents, selecting interviewees, and interviewing and analysing interviewee responses.

3.1. Review of relevant documents

The document analysis (see Table 1) followed a systematic approach focusing on how climate adaptation has been mainstreamed into sectoral policies since 22 August 1992, after the country ratified the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). The systematic procedure consists of searching and synthesizing research evidence on the state of knowledge on a given topic or based on research questions (Epule et al., 2017; Okpara et al., 2018). Keywords used during the search include: ‘climate/climatic change adaptation’, ‘drought’, ‘flood’, ‘mitigation’, ‘environmental protection’, ‘environmental education’, and ‘climate change communication’. The search generated 25 policy documents, including strategies and action plans (Table 1). Mainstreaming is said to have occurred when (i) climate change adaptation/mitigation is mentioned in the policy document(s) and (ii) specific actions are included to account for and enable the mainstreaming of climate adaptation. In this study, sectoral policy refers to any initiatives or projects put in place by the government to integrate climate adaptation in the already-mentioned sectors.

Table 1: List of documents reviewed

Document title	Sector	Source and year
Seychelles Updated Nationally Determined Contribution	Cross-cutting	GoS (2021)
Seychelles National Climate Change Policy	Cross-cutting	GoS (2020a)
Seychelles Protected Areas Policy	Biodiversity	GoS (2013a)
Seychelles' National Biodiversity and Action Plan 2015-2020	Biodiversity	GoS (2014b)
Seychelles National Climate Change and Health Adaptation Plan of Action 2014-2018	Health	MoH & MEECC (2013)
Seychelles National Food and Nutrition Security Policy	Agriculture	GoS (2013b)
Seychelles National Agriculture Investment Plan	Agriculture	GoS (2015a)
Seychelles National Agroforestry Policy	Agriculture	SNAP (2021)
Seychelles Wetlands Policy and Action Plan 2019-2022	Cross-cutting	GoS (2019b)
Seychelles Fishing Authority Strategic Plan 2018-2020	Fisheries	SFA (2018)
Seychelles Water Supply Development Plan 2008-2030	Water	African Water Facility (2008)
Seychelles Port Authority Strategic Plan 2019- 2023	Cross-cutting	SPA (2019)
Environment Management Plan of Seychelles 1990-2000	Cross-cutting	GoS (1990)
Environment Management Plan of Seychelles 2000-2010	Cross-cutting	GoS (2000)
Proposal for Energy Policy of the Republic of Seychelles 2010-2030	Energy	GoS (2010)
Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan	Blue Economy	GoS (2015b)
Seychelles Coastal Management Plan 2019-2024	Coastal Management	World Bank & MEECC (2019)
Seychelles Blue Economy Strategic Policy and Roadmap: Charting the Future 2018-2030	Blue Economy	GoS (2018)
Seychelles National Climate Change Strategy	Cross-cutting	GoS (2009)
Seychelles National Forest Policy and Legislation	Biodiversity	GoS (2020b)
Seychelles National Integrated Emergency Risk Management Plan	Cross-cutting	World Bank & DRDM (2019)
Seychelles' Initial National Communication under the UNFCCC	Cross-cutting	GoS (2000a)
Seychelles' Second National Communication under the UNFCCC	Cross-cutting	GoS (2011)
Seychelles National Development Strategy 2019-2023	Cross-cutting	GoS (2019)
Seychelles Sustainable Development Strategy 2012-2020	Cross-cutting	GoS (2012)

3.2. Selecting interviewees and interviewing

An inventory of institutions responsible for mainstreaming climate adaptation/mitigation into sectoral policies either directly or indirectly was carried out using two criteria: (a) function, and (b) knowledge and abilities. Potential interviewees had to meet the following four criteria: (i) had oversight of climate change, environment, and/or development portfolio in a government agency, sector, or department; (ii) have been part of the climate change discourse in Seychelles for at least five years; (iii) well-versed in adaptation in Seychelles' context; and (iv) confirmed their availability and consent to participate in the interview. Additionally, a snowball sampling technique was employed to identify other interviewees. This technique uses participants to recommend others that are essential for participating in the interview (Atkinson and Flint, 2001; Streeton et al., 2004) who fulfill criteria 1 to 3. This resulted in 34 stakeholders being selected for interview (see Table 2). A semi-structured interview technique was applied to the relevant stakeholders. This

approach was chosen because a significant benefit is that participants are more likely to express their views (Flick, 2009) openly. To maintain anonymity, each interviewee was assigned a code. Interviews lasted 30- 60 minutes and were conducted in English and Creole. These interviews took place from July 21st to October 27th, 2021, and were audio recorded; in most instances, notes were taken.

Table 2: Summary of stakeholders interviewed by institution and organization

Structure	No of Participants	Type of Organization
Ministry of Fisheries and Blue Economy	3	Government
Department of Environment (MACCE)	4	Government
Department of Agriculture (MACCE)	2	Government
Department of Energy and Climate Change (MACCE)	4	Government
Land Transport Department (MHILT)	1	Government
Tourism Department (MFAT)	2	Government
University	10	Academia
Citizens Engagement Platform Seychelles (CEPS)	2	Civil Society
Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT)	2	NGO
United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)	2	IO

NGO: *Non-Governmental Organization*

IO: *International Organization*

MACCE: *Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment*

MHILT: *Ministry of Habitat, Infrastructure, and Land Transport*

MFAT: *Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Tourism*

3.3. Analysing interviewee responses

The five-step process outlined by McCracken (1998) was applied in analysing the responses from the interviewees. In the first step, voice-recorded interviews were listened to closely, twice; while interview notes in cases without voice recording were also read twice. In the second step, initial interpretive and descriptive categories were identified. For the third step, categories identified in step two and constituting initial codes were used to identify further patterns in the data. Broad themes were identified by clustering a single interviewee's responses as the fourth step. In the fifth and last steps, these broad themes were examined across all interviews, and predominant themes are presented in the result section of this paper.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. To what extent has climate change adaptation been mainstreamed into sectoral policies?

Since the Rio Earth Summit in 1992, climate change adaptation has become a topical issue in Seychelles. The process has been guided by different policies and plans that integrate climate risks within the social and economic development sectors (GoS, 2021). Seychelles' response to climate change and environmental protection is also reflected in the country's national climate change policy (GoS, 2020a), and adaptation is given greater priority due to the vulnerability of the island state to the impacts of climate change (GoS, 2020a; GoS, 2015c; GoS, 2012). The long history of climate adaptation into policies and strategies could be traced to Seychelles' Initial and Second National Communication to the UNFCCC (2000a; GoS, 2011).

Guided by a sector approach, the recently updated NDC gives priority to the following strategic actions such as nature-based solutions to protect coastal ecosystems; adapting an integrated Ridge-to-Reef (R2R) approach to coastal management; developing a Port Master Plan; improving the management of freshwater resources; among others (GoS, 2021). Chapter 4 of the Second National Communication to the UNFCCC focuses entirely on vulnerability and adaptation measures. It outlines existing adaptation measures and options to enhance its mainstreaming into policies and national development plans (Mogelgaard et al., 2018). The reviewed policy documents and the stakeholder interviews were used to answer the question: 'To what extent has climate adaptation been mainstreamed into sectoral policies?' Details of these findings are presented for each sector.

4.1.1. Forestry Sector

National policy in the forestry sector is rooted in environmental policy as described in the Environmental Management Plans of Seychelles (EMPS 1990- 2000) and other international conventions. Examples of such conventions include the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD); the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC); Chapter 11 of the Agenda 21 of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) on Deforestation; the Forest Principles of UNCED (GoS, 1990). Moreover, Seychelles' Protected Areas Policy is another important policy document that reinforces Seychelles' position of legally protecting 47% of the total land area (GoS, 2013a). Also, this policy document references the Forestry Reserves Act of 1955 which sets out provisions for the designation of 'forest reserves'. A further development was the Seychelles National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan 2015-2020 (NBSAP), which addresses issues relevant to adaptation, such as financing, capacity building, and climate-related

biodiversity issues (2014b).

4.1.2. Agricultural Sector

The Seychelles Sustainable Development Strategy (SSDS) is an important document that addresses adaptation mainstreaming across sectors inclusive of agriculture. One of the five focus areas outlined in the SSDS is food security, trade, and diversification (GoS, 2012). A significant milestone in this sector is the Seychelles National Food and Nutrition Security Policy (SNFNSP), which provided an enabling environment for mainstreaming climate adaptation in the agricultural sector (2013b). Though mainstreaming wasn't evident in the 90s during the Initial National Communication (INC) to the UNFCCC (initiated in 1993), it has gained traction in Seychelles since 2015 when the water-energy-food nexus approach became a central tenet of some environmental projects in Seychelles (Etongo, 2022).

Despite being a tropical island with sufficient rainfall to support rain-fed agriculture, Seychelles' agricultural sector highly depends on irrigation (Etongo et al., 2022). One possible explanation is the predominance of the ferritic soil, commonly known as '*la Terre Rouge*' or red soil, originating from the weathering of granitic rock and having low water retention capacity. Therefore, access to water is essential for food production, and wetland restoration has gained traction in Seychelles. It is promoted mainly by the Department of Agriculture (DoA) as a nature-based solution for farmers to access water for irrigation. The Seychelles National Agricultural Investment Plan (SNAIP) 2015- 2020 has enhanced the mainstreaming of agriculture into cross-sector policies, especially within the water-energy-food nexus. One of the programmes outlined in the SNAIP is to protect and sustain agricultural lands and water use. In line with such programmes, climate-smart farming practices have been promoted among farmers through donor-funded projects by the FAO (FAO and ICRISAT, 2019). Examples of some climate-smart practices include using drought-resistant crops such as root crops (cassava, sweet potato) and maize on the one hand, and rainwater harvesting, streams, rivers, and boreholes to irrigate farmlands – an ongoing practice for over three decades.

4.1.3. Health Sector

Climate change will affect the occurrence and spread of diseases in Seychelles, and a few recent crises (e.g., dengue fever) signalled the need to adapt proactively (IMF, 2017). Although climate adaptation responses in the health sector are relatively new, some progress has been made. Despite minimal implementation, health considerations were captured in the Environmental Management Plans (GoS, 1990; GoS, 2000a) and the Seychelles Sustainable Development Strategy – SSDS [61]. A significant step towards mainstreaming climate adaptation in this sector is the development of the Health National Action Plan (HNAP) for Seychelles (MoH and

MEECC, 2013). This action plan addresses the health adaptation process at the national level, which can potentially mitigate climate-related impacts on health (MoH and MEECC, 2013).

Collaboration with the vital ministry responsible for climate change is another strategy that has enhanced mainstream climate adaptation in the health sector. For example, the MEECC, currently known as the Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE), together with the Ministry of Health (MoH), collaborate on an ad-hoc basis on events such as the management of disease outbreaks, environmental pollution and other specific programmes to address health and environmental matters. Mainstreaming climate adaptation in these sectors has occurred partly by improving conditions for healthy living. For example, the new Building Codes by the Seychelles Planning Authority (SPA) for residential and commercial buildings now provide co-benefit for mitigation and adaptation to climate change through specifications to adopt solar PV, rainwater-harvesting systems, double-glazed windows, and to promote the greening of public spaces such as parks (Etongo, 2021).

4.1.4. Energy Sector

The main climate adaptation policy mainstreamed in the energy sector revolves around promoting the country's use of renewable energy and energy efficiency (Hadush and Bhagwat, 2019). Interestingly, the Seychelles Sustainable Development Strategy (SSDS) 2012-2020 incorporates national priorities for sustainable development and formulates guiding principles for the energy and transport sector (GoS, 2012). According to the strategy, the 'reliance on fossil fuels should be gradually reduced as they are not sustainable sources', and the 'energy independence should be increased to reduce economic vulnerability through local energy sources'. The legislated renewable energy consumption targets are 5% by 2020 and 15% by 2030, as outlined in the 2010 Energy Policy (GoS, 2010). The energy policy provides several attractive incentives to facilitate the uptake of renewable energy technologies, especially rooftop PV to increase the resilience of Seychelles' energy sector to climate change and variability (Wehner et al., 2020). As far back as April 2017, inhabitants of the three main islands of Seychelles could exchange two of their incandescent light bulbs for LED (light-emitting diode) bulbs (Seychelles News Agency, 2017). Under the renewable energy policy, several projects on biomass to energy, solar hot water, solar PV, and wind energy have been implemented across the Seychelles.

Energy provides input into almost all other sectors of an economy, facilitating and propelling activities in these sectors, including water, food, agriculture and forestry, natural-disaster response, blue-economy development, and human health. As many sector adaptation measures require energy provision, energy can be an adaptation enabler for other sectors and areas. For instance, energy service is a fundamental

input in the water, agriculture, and food industries, with the water-energy-food (WEF) nexus promoted as an approach to enhance co-benefits for adaptation and mitigation (Etongo, 2022). Energy service enables energy-intensive processes in the water sector (e.g., collection, purification, desalination, storage, distribution, treatment, and drainage) and food supply (e.g., land preparation, cultivation, irrigation, fertilizing, processing, storage, transport, distribution, and consumption), which are often connected to energy infrastructure.

4.1.5. Water Sector

Water is at the heart of adaptation to climate change, serving as the crucial link between the climate system, human society, and the environment. The laws governing the water sector in Seychelles are contained in different pieces of legislation (Port-Louis, 2021). More importantly, the Seychelles National Water Policy is influenced by, and strives to contribute to achieving, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with an emphasis on SDG 6 which elucidates goals for the provision of clean water and sanitation, and SDGs 13, 14, and 15 that deal with climate action, life below water and life on land. The Government of Seychelles has also promoted integrated water management for over a decade. This management strategy has focused on energy efficiency, demand management, and developing alternative supply sources from rainwater harvesting and water use.

Adopted in July 2017, the National Water Policy and National Integrated Water Resource Management Plan reinforced the momentum of water management (World Water, 2017). Access to water resources as an adaptation strategy has been promoted for domestic and agricultural uses. For example, rainwater harvesting systems have been incorporated in educational establishments and smallholder farming systems with support from international NGOs, local NGOs, and the MACCE and Ministry of Education. In some cases, wetlands have been restored to provide farmers with access to water as part of the Ecosystem-Based Adaptation to Climate Change in the Seychelles Project. Therefore, adaptation has been mainstreamed effectively in the water sector despite some areas needing further improvement.

4.1.6. Blue Economy Sector

To avoid duplication, the Blue Economy (BE) within the context of this study focuses on coastal management, fisheries and aquaculture, tourism, and critical infrastructure sectors. A significant development in this sector is the Blue Economy Strategic Policy Framework and Roadmap 2018 – 2030 (GoS, 2018). This framework and roadmap provide an approach to ocean-based sustainable development which brings the economy, the environment, and society together towards achieving global agendas such as the Sustainable Development Goals 2030, Target 11 of the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the Paris Agreement. Mainstreaming

climate change adaptation into the different sub-sectors of the BE also features prominently in the Seychelles Updated Nationally Determined Contribution to the UNFCCC (GoS, 2021).

The Seychelles Strategic and Land Use Plan, which guides land-use management from 2015-2040, also considers adaptation mainstreaming within the BE sector (GoS, 2015b). This has led to climate-proofing development fully integrated into the New Building Codes in Seychelles. Also, Seychelles' management of coastal wetlands falls under the Environment Protection Act and the Seychelles Wetland Policy and Action Plan (GoS, 2019b). A particular focus has been given to coastal wetlands for mitigation and adaptation co-benefits in line with the development of the blue carbon concept (Herr and Landis, 2016), which has gained traction in Seychelles and is primarily promoted by Seychelles' Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT). Coral restoration also has a long history in the island state. The Nature Seychelles Reef Rescuers programme has grown 45,000 corals in underwater nurseries, representing the world's most extensive coral reef restoration programme (GoS, 2018).

Regarding the fishery sector, the overall policy framework is captured in the Seychelles Fisheries Sector Policy and Strategy 2019 (SPA, 2019). This document aims towards long-term sustainable fishery and aquaculture management and conservation to ensure its crucial role in the country's sustainable development. The fisheries sector is regulated by six critical pieces of legislation (SPA, 2019). In 2018, Seychelles National Aquaculture Policy 2018-2022 was published. The policy's aim is 'guiding an effectively managed and environmentally responsible aquaculture industry that contributes towards food security and the creation of wealth in Seychelles' (SFA, 2018).

Concerning tourism, the Tourism Master Plan describes the objective to develop a tourism plan specific for Mahe, Praslin, La Digue, and the Outer Islands, given that the impact of climate change is not equally distributed across the Seychelles group of islands (GoS, 2018). A significant milestone in this sector is the Seychelles Sustainable Tourism Label (SSTL), introduced in 2011. The mission of the SSTL is to encourage hotels in Seychelles to mainstream sustainability practices into their business operation to safeguard the biodiversity and culture of Seychelles. Sustainability is promoted in the following seven areas; management, waste, water, energy, staff, conservation, community, and agents. However, most hotels that conform to these practices are luxury hotels. Regarding climate change adaptation, initiatives such as rainwater harvesting, gardening, renewable energy, energy efficiency, and waste management are promoted in the tourism industry.

4.2. What are the constraints impeding adaptation mainstreaming?

Despite some efforts made by the Government of Seychelles during the last ten years to mainstream climate adaptation into sectoral policies, most stakeholders recognized that numerous challenges still impede the mainstreaming initiative in the country. These constraints based on the stakeholder interviews are grouped into the following categories as follows: (i) policy and governance constraints, (ii) insufficient financial resources, (iii) risk of diminishing visibility and attention, and (iv) human resource capacity.

4.2.1. Policy and governance constraints

Climate change is a cross-cutting issue, and there is a need for policy harmonization to ensure alignment on the one hand and cross-sectoral collaboration on the other. One of the constraints mentioned was the Seychelles National Climate Change Strategy which was crafted by the National Climate Change Committee in 2009. While this strategy guided climate-proofing national development in Seychelles, an updated and revised climate strategy is overdue. A recently updated climate change strategy could have informed the NDC of Seychelles (GoS, 2021). Instead, the updated NDC seems to have replaced the climate change strategy, whereas both documents must complement each other. Therefore, policy coherence is still a work in progress. The Seychelles case represents a broader policy challenge relevant to a similar set of countries – vulnerable island states (Robinson, 2017) and developing countries (Runhaar et al., 2018). In most cases, revising climate-related policies and strategies depends on external donor funding, which might not be available on time. For this reason, some policies and plans that the government could have revised are still in use.

Adaptation is cross-cutting, involving multiple sectors and actors within a multilevel governance structure with different power relations and resource access. More importantly, public-private partnership is crucial for resource-use efficiency and ensuring adaptation initiatives' sustainability. However, the effectiveness of such partnerships may vary from country to country. For example, private sector engagement in climate change issues in Seychelles has been fragile (Etongo, 2019). Although the climate change policy (GoS, 2020a) makes provision for a National Climate Change Council (NCCC) with representatives from the private sector to be nominated by the Seychelles Chamber of Commerce and Industry (SCCI), this council is yet to be established. Policy and governance constraints are further compounded by the problem of competing priorities and the more urgent need to address short-term priorities rather than long-term climate risks – a view supported by an earlier study in the Pacific and Caribbean SIDS (Robinson, 2017). This is an issue of concern since medium- and long-term adaptation delivers benefits by

averting the risk of future damage rather than generating more immediate and tangible benefits.

4.2.2. Insufficient financial resources

It was clear from all the stakeholders interviewed that financial resources were insufficient to implement or maintain adaptation initiatives in Seychelles. Despite highlighting some financial support received from international organizations such as the Adaptation Fund (AF), Global Environment Facility (GEF), and Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), the lack of financial resources for continuity was cited as a significant barrier. Funds were provided to the Government of Seychelles through the 'Global Funds for Adaptation' and the European Union for pilot projects implemented at specific sites, such as the drainage and erosion project on La Digue (Hassan, 2020). However, coastal erosion and flash floods persist, and the budget allocation does not cover all the hot-spot sites across the Seychelles. Inadequate technologies and infrastructures were key concerns stakeholders raised as a barrier to insufficient financial resources.

Access to financial resources nationally for adaptation projects is limited. The Environment Trust Fund (ETF) and the Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT) are the funding sources that were recurrent among stakeholders, but this isn't enough to address all the nations' needs. One stakeholder mentioned that the 'US\$100 billion a year to Non-Annex 1 countries (developing countries including SIDS) by 2020, to mitigate and adapt to climate change is yet to be met'. As climate change impacts become increasingly apparent, adaptation becomes increasingly urgent, especially in SIDS, which are more vulnerable to the effects of climate change; and financial resources are needed to implement projects that can enhance the adaptive capacities of these nations. However, a recent study also showed the \$100-billion target was out of reach (Robert et al., 2021), which further constrains Non-Annex 1 countries in achieving their adaptation targets as outlined in nationally determined contributions (NDCs). Therefore, financial resources remain a crucial constraint to climate adaptation into national development, given that the USD 339 million across the nine adaptation sectors in Seychelles is yet to receive funding (GoS, 2021). The consequence, therefore, is translating proposed projects into actions on the ground as the NDC is conditional upon the availability of funds from Annex 1 countries.

4.2.3. Risks of diminishing issue visibility and attention

Climate adaptation mainstreaming requires targeted strategies and actions beyond mere aspirations in order to be effective. Though the reviewed policy documents contain components of adaptation, the issue of mainstreaming became apparent during the last ten years. Despite such recorded progress, there wasn't any accepted

agreement about what mainstreaming is to achieve, i.e. when it is effective, and how this could be measured – a critical barrier that other studies have raised (Runhaar et al., 2018; Brouwer et al., 2013; Adelle and Russel, 2013; Etongo et al., 2020). As such, mainstreaming is likely to have occurred as a positive side-effect rather than a conscious strategy fully integrated into sector plans and strategies and, more importantly, national development strategies. The implication, therefore, is that sectorial rather than cross-sectoral objectives are given more attention. For example, most stakeholders during the interviews believed that climate change is the responsibility of the MACCE. Such popular belief quickly diminishes the integration of climate adaptation into other sector policies and strategies on the one hand and, on the other hand, weakens the participation of these different sectors in the national climate change dialogue.

4.2.4. Human resource capacity

Mainstreaming climate adaptation into sectorial policies would require knowledge of adaptation and what action plans or strategies can be implemented across sectors to improve their adaptive capacities to the impacts of climate change. These constraints partly link to having staff across different sectors with trans-disciplinary backgrounds on climate adaptation and how it can be integrated into sectorial policies. For example, stakeholders in the health sectors could quickly identify actions that have been mainstreamed into their sector, such as energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy to reduce carbon dioxide emissions. But when interviewed on adaptation mainstreaming, the stakeholders had a minimal idea of how this could be done within the health sector – an indication of human resource capacity to address this need. The small population size of Seychelles also raises issues of human resources capacity which have been identified by another study on mainstreaming climate adaptation in the Pacific and Caribbean SIDS (Robinson, 2017). Respondents also mentioned that employment staff often encounter difficulties getting a release to further their education at the University of Seychelles or abroad. Therefore, new knowledge and skills needed to enhance effective climate adaptation mainstreaming into sector policies, strategies, and action plans are lacking or, in some instances, very minimal.

4.3. Stakeholders' recommendations

Irrespective of the difficulties expressed by stakeholders that hinder mainstreaming climate adaptation into the health, water, agriculture, energy, forestry, and Blue Economy sectors, proposals were made to fast-track the mainstreaming process.

In the area of research, more than half of the stakeholders interviewed thought that, while searching for ways to facilitate the mainstreaming of climate adaptation into different sectorial policies, the government should consider the allocation of financial

resources to the University of Seychelles, especially for the Blue Economy Research Institute – a view supported by a recent study in Seychelles (Vergouwen et al., 2021). They argued that such initiatives have the potential to increase the research output from a country-based institution, directly address the needs of the policymakers, increase collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and local communities, and could help to upgrade research facilities at the University of Seychelles and also enhance capacity-building through collaborative research with government institutions, for example, the MACCE and other NGOs.

Other stakeholders cautioned that policymakers should encourage researchers to carry out long-term climate impact studies, which are helpful for mainstreaming policies aimed at long-term climate-resilient development, instead of concentrating on short time frames guided by politics and immediate development priorities. Such recommendations are commendable, considering that the most severe impacts of climate change may become visible only in the long term. Identifying local governance capacity needs for implementing climate change adaptation in Seychelles was mentioned as a priority area of research that needed urgent attention. One of the stakeholders said that the District Authorities (DAs) are the gatekeepers to the communities and should be equipped with the technical skills needed to address climate change issues and location-specific adaptation. Identifying and integrating local capacity needs into policy measures can improve multilevel governance and the effective implementation of National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), given that local governments in Seychelles have contextual knowledge about their territories and the climate change challenges affecting them (Etongo and Gill, 2022).

Considering the significant deficit in the number of climate scientists in Seychelles, many stakeholders interviewed proposed that, to raise awareness among pupils and students and encourage them to develop an interest in climate science, the government, in partnership with development partners, could put in place a strategy to install simple weather stations in schools across the country. According to them, installing such weather equipment in schools can arouse curiosity among pupils and students, thereby encouraging them to develop an interest in climate science which could reduce the deficit in climate scientists in the long term.

To reduce the communication gap and make climate information more accessible to the general public, some of the stakeholders interviewed proposed that the government and other partners could put in place different categories of monthly/annual prizes to compensate local media organizations and journalists that run regular programmes or report issues on climate change and environmental protection. It was also proposed that training workshops should be organized with local stakeholders such as members of the National Assembly, DAs, NGOs, CBOs, and faith-based leaders who can mobilize and influence the local population to train

them on climate issues, given that this group of people can quickly disseminate climate information to community members if they are sufficiently informed.

Regarding adaptation financing, stakeholders articulated that since most government ministries/institutions directly involved with climate issues have less financial autonomy to mainstream climate adaptation into long-term development plans at different sectoral levels, specialized units could be created in influential ministries responsible for finance and economic planning. They argued that creating such units in the said ministry may fast-track the mainstreaming of climate adaptation into the country's long-term development plans. However, it was cautioned that for such plans to be successful, there is a need to train more climate scientists to take up such roles in public administration with the ability to provide realistic budgeting on adaptation programmes and projects in national development strategies. Additionally, a fundraising role through private sector actors and NGOs was recommended by three stakeholders for the Seychelles Conservation and Climate Adaptation Trust (SeyCCAT) to ensure it becomes sustainable over time.

5. Conclusion

Mainstreaming climate adaptation into sectoral policies can support compatible development that addresses the needs of NDC and Sustainable Development Goals. While climate adaptation features prominently in most climate change policies and action plans, mainstreaming has been featured in recent documents during the last ten years. Some strategic documents that guided adaptation mainstreaming were obsolete and didn't align with important climate policy documents. The case of Seychelles represents a broader policy challenge relevant for a similar set of countries, e.g., small island states and developing countries that are highly dependent on external donor funding to produce or update important policy documents related to climate change.

Analysis complemented by stakeholder interviews indicates that many obstacles, such as inadequate human and financial resources, need to be addressed to enhance climate adaptation mainstreaming, especially in the health, agriculture, and Blue Economy sectors. Seychelles became a high-income country in 2015 with limited access to specific categories of funding that are mainly allocated to low and middle-income countries. Although institutions such as the Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE) have been put in place to facilitate mainstreaming climate adaptation into sectoral policies, cross-sectoral coordination is still lacking. Human resource capacity building should be promoted among government staff on climate-related issues to ensure that knowledge on adaptation

for sector-specific mainstreaming is achieved. Lastly, Seychelles' national development strategy offers the best opportunity for climate change mainstreaming into development programmes and projects across sectors.

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